
Job Satisfaction And Incentives Determine The Welfare Of The GIG Workforce In The Food And Beverage Industry In Mumbai Metropolitan Region

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15100900

Abstract:

The labour market has evolved with technology, customer expectations, job contracts, and workforce knowledge. The food and beverage industry in Mumbai Metropolitan Region (MMR) is no exception. Economic growth and high per capita income have increased service expectations at lower costs. Our survey of workers in this sector reveals a predominance of young unmarried female graduates over males. Women generally lack vehicle licenses and ownership, and debit/credit card usage is low. Workers rarely own household assets like cars or washing machines and lack access to skill upgradation, provident funds, health insurance, maternity/paternity leave, or other benefits. Logistic regression indicates that job satisfaction is positively correlated with education and home assets like air conditioners and refrigerators but negatively with incentives, radio and bike ownership. Ensuring social security benefits and financial incentives can improve workers welfare in food and beverage industry.

Keywords: *Skills, Technology, Income*

Introduction:

The gig economy, characterized by short-term contracts and flexible work, has grown significantly worldwide, accelerated by digital platforms and technological advancements. While gig work offers autonomy, it often lacks stability, benefits, and labour rights. In India, the gig workforce is projected to expand to 23.5 million by 2029-30, forming 6.7% of the non-agricultural workforce (NITI Aayog, 2022). The food and beverage industry in Mumbai Metropolitan Region (MMR) has seen significant participation from gig workers. However, due to economic constraints and cost-cutting measures, they often lack social security and stable earnings, making job satisfaction a major concern.

GIG Workers in the Food and Beverage Industry in Mumbai Metropolitan Region (MMR):

Mumbai Metropolitan Region (MMR) has rapid urbanization and rising disposable incomes of people. Therefore, it has driven demand for dining services. High-income consumers expect prompt and quality services, leading food establishments to employ a mix of skilled and unskilled gig workers. These workers engage in hourly or part-time roles, from food preparation to delivery. Women, particularly young graduates dominate employment in this sector, often due to familiarity with food preparation and service. However, post-marriage responsibilities, long

shifts, and lack of maternity leave significantly impact female workers. They leave the jobs due to lower payment, job satisfaction and lack of social security benefits.

Data Collection and Analysis:

We developed questionnaire based on literature review of food and beverage sector. Based on questionnaire, we collected primary data of 300 workers across Mumbai Metropolitan Region. The primary data was collected from May to August 2024. The area is divided as Western, Central, Eastern suburb of Mumbai, and Navi Mumbai suburb. We have used SPSS@26 and R software for data analysis. We have examined socioeconomic and demographic backgrounds, working conditions, job incentives, and satisfaction levels of the workers working in food and beverage industry. We measured workers job satisfaction based on different criteria. It is further regressed on socio-economic and demographic variables of workers working in food and beverage units in Mumbai Metropolitan Region.

Economic Model:

We have developed an economic model after considering the population and socio-economic and demographic factors of the population in the region.

$$P_{mmr} = (P_{Ma} - P_{MR}) \quad (1)$$

The population in the Mumbai Metropolitan Region is calculated as the population of Maharashtra minus the population of the rest of Maharashtra.

$$\sum P = f(E, TW, TE, FE) \quad (2)$$

Age is categorised as E means eighteen to twenty eight (18-28) age group, TW is twenty eight to thirty eight (28-38) age group, TE means thirty eight to forty eight (38-48) age category, FE means forty eight to fifty eight (48-58) age group.

$$M_s = f(M, UM, S, D) \quad (3)$$

We categorized marital status of workers as M as married workers, UM as unmarried, S as separated, and D as divorced types of marriage for workers.

$$\sum R_w = f(H, C, M, S, J) \quad (4)$$

Religion of the workers (R_w) is divided as H means Hindu, C is Christian, M defined as Muslim, S stands for Sikh, and J is Jain.

$$E_w = (Il, Se, Hs, Gr, Pgr) \quad (5)$$

Education of workers in region is categorised as Il means Illiterate, Se stands for Secondary education, Hs means High Secondary School Gr is Graduate and Pgr related to postgraduate degree of worker.

$$P_d = (Dl, Dv, P, Ba, Cc, Dc, Rc) \quad (6)$$

Personal documents are categorised as Dl as Driving licence, Dv means driving vehicle as drive two and four-wheeler, P is Passport, Ba means Bank account, Cc deals with Credit card owned by workers at the same time DC is defined as Debit card and RC stands for Ration card.

$$Y_{wt} = (Tt, Tth, Thr, Fo, Fa) \quad (7)$$

Income of worker at time t is categorised as Ywt. It is further categorised as Tt means Rs.10-20 thousand per month. The Tth is Rs.20-30 thousand per month. The Thr is Rs.30-40 thousand per month at the same time the Fo means monthly income of worker is Rs40-50 thousand per month. Lastly Fa is Rs.50 thousand and above income of workers.

$$\sum_n^t A_w = (R, T, O, B, Cy, Ca, Wm, Ac, R) \quad (8)$$

Aw means assets at home. Here R means Radio and T means Television at home. The O defined as Oven and B means Bike as well as Cy stands for Cycle. The Ca is Car owned by

worker and Wm means Washing machine at home. At the same time Ac is Air conditioner whereas R stands for Refrigerator at home.

Socioeconomic and Demographic Characteristics:

We have studied a few socio-economic and demographic factors that are related to gig workers in the food and beverage industry. They are discussed as follows.

Table 1 - Age Group of GIG Workers in Mumbai Region (%)

Suburbs	Gender	18-28	28-38	38-48	48-58
	M	34.26	37.96	21.30	6.48
Western	F	50.79	44.44	3.17	1.59
	T	51.49	34.33	5.22	8.96
	M	53.85	30.77	11.54	3.85
Central	F	52.94	47.06	0.00	0.00
	T	58.97	27.35	7.69	5.98
	M	30.77	38.46	23.08	7.69
Eastern	F	37.50	50.00	12.50	0.00
	T	67.57	16.22	10.81	5.41
	M	50.00	28.57	14.29	7.14
Navi Mumbai	F	62.50	37.50	0.00	0.00
	T	66.67	16.67	8.33	16.67
	M	40.64	35.29	18.18	5.88
Total	F	51.33	45.13	2.65	0.88
	T	57.00	28.67	7.00	7.67

Source: Calculated from Primary data

The table shows that females (62.50%) from Navi Mumbai and males (53.85%) from the Western suburbs in the 18-28 age group are working in the food and beverage sector. This indicates that more females are engaged in the food and beverage industry in the region. Females do not require much training because they know how to cook and serve food to customers. Since childhood, they have been observing such things at home as well. The male (38.46%) and female (50%) workers from the Eastern suburbs are in the 28-38 age group. In this age group, we found the maximum number of female workers in this sector. More males (23.08%) than females (12.50%) from the Eastern suburbs in the 38-48 age group are working in this industry. The males (7.69%) from the Eastern suburbs and females (1.59%) from the Western suburbs are working in the 48-58 age group. As the age of the worker increases, employment in this industry decreases. Older workers either do not get higher pay or are not ready to work in the food and beverage industry. In the 38-48 and 48-58 age groups, a similar percentage of workers are employed in this sector.

Table 2 - Marital Status of GIG Workers (%)

Suburbs		Married	Unmarried	Separated	Divorced
	M	39.81	58.33	0.93	0.93
Western	F	19.05	77.78	0.00	3.17
	T	32.16	65.50	0.58	1.75
	M	32.69	67.31	0.00	0.00
Central	F	11.76	88.24	0.00	0.00
	T	24.42	75.58	0.00	0.00
	M	46.15	53.85	0.00	0.00
Eastern	F	37.50	62.50	0.00	0.00
	T	42.86	57.14	0.00	0.00

	M	28.57	71.43	0.00	0.00
Navi Mumbai	F	0.00	87.50	12.50	0.00
	T	18.18	77.27	4.55	0.00
	M	37.43	61.50	0.53	0.53
Total	F	16.81	80.53	0.88	1.77
	T	29.67	68.67	0.67	1.00

Source: As per table 1

Unmarried and educated workers can spend more time learning skills. Marriage restricts the freedom to upgrade skills due to time constraints. The males (46.15%) from the Western suburbs and females (37.50%) from the Eastern suburbs are married but are working in food and beverage units. The males (71.43%) from Navi Mumbai and females (88.24%) from the Central suburbs are unmarried. This indicates that the maximum number of unmarried females and males are working in this sector. After completing their education, females join the food and beverage industry immediately. The males (0.93%) from the Western suburbs and 12.50% of females from Navi Mumbai are separated but are workers in the food and beverage industry. The 0.93% of males and 3.17% of females from the Western suburbs are divorced. Very few divorced males are working in this sector. There are different reasons for their marital status. We can say that the maximum number of workers (68.67%) in food and beverage units are unmarried. With lower salaries and a lower cost of living, these workers can afford to live in the city. The majority are traveling from the longer distance by local trains for work.

Table 3 - Religious Background Of GIG Workers (%)

Suburbs	Religion	Hindu	Christian	Muslim	Sikh	Jain
	M	82.41	5.56	11.11	0.93	0.00
Western	F	92.06	0.00	6.35	0.00	1.59
	T	85.96	3.51	9.36	0.58	0.58
	M	84.62	0.00	13.46	0.00	1.92
Central	F	82.35	5.88	11.76	0.00	0.00
	T	83.72	2.33	12.79	0.00	1.16
	M	84.62	0.00	7.69	0.00	7.69
Eastern	F	75.00	0.00	12.50	0.00	12.50
	T	80.95	0.00	9.52	0.00	9.52
	M	64.29	7.14	21.43	0.00	7.14
Navi Mumbai	F	100	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	T	77.27	4.55	13.64	0.00	4.55
	M	81.82	3.74	12.30	0.53	1.60
Total	F	88.50	1.77	7.96	0.00	1.77
	T	84.33	3.00	10.67	0.33	1.67

Source: As per table 1

Nearly 92.06% of females are Hindu from the Western suburbs, whereas all women found in Navi Mumbai belong to the Hindu religion. A total of 5.56% of male workers are Christian, but they are from the Western suburbs. Around 5.88% of women are from the Central suburbs and are Christian (21.43%) of males are from Navi Mumbai and belong to the Muslim community. From the Eastern suburbs, 12.50% of females are from the Muslim community. Only 0.93% of males from the Sikh community are from the Western suburbs but are working in the food and beverage industry. No female labour from the Sikh community was found in the region. Males (7.69%) and females (12.50%) of the Jain community are from the Eastern suburbs and are

working in the food and beverage industry. This means that 84.33% of workers are from the Hindu religion and are working in the food and beverage industry in the region. The majority of workers in the food and beverage industry are from the Hindu religion. The educational achievement of workers certainly provides more skills and learning abilities.

Table 4 - Educational Qualification Of GIG Workers In Mumbai Region (%)

Region	Gender	Illiterate	Secondary	Higher secondary	Graduate	Postgraduate
	M	9.26	16.67	22.22	48.15	3.70
Western	F	3.17	12.70	31.75	50.79	1.59
	T	7.02	15.20	25.73	49.12	2.92
	M	15.38	23.08	17.31	44.23	0.00
Central	F	2.94	23.53	17.65	55.88	0.00
	T	10.47	23.26	17.44	48.84	0.00
	M	38.46	30.77	0.00	30.77	0.00
Eastern	F	12.50	0.00	37.50	50.00	0.00
	T	28.57	19.05	14.29	38.10	0.00
	M	7.14	14.29	21.43	57.14	0.00
Navi Mumbai	F	12.50	12.50	50.00	25.00	0.00
	T	9.09	13.64	31.82	45.45	0.00
	M	12.83	19.25	19.25	46.52	2.14
Total	F	4.42	15.04	29.20	50.44	0.88
	T	9.67	17.67	23.00	48.00	1.67

Source: As per table 1

Workers in the food and beverage industry have lower educational achievements. Highly educated workers may expect good contracts with higher pay from employers, but this sector is not well-paid based on education and skills. From the above table, we can observe that males (38.46%) and females (12.50%) are illiterate, but they are from the Eastern region. We have not studied their designations and salaries, but they would likely be delivery persons or waiters. 23.08% of males and 23.53% of females are from the Central suburbs and have completed secondary education while working in the food and beverage industry. A total of half of the females and 21.43% of males are from Navi Mumbai and have completed higher secondary education. This means more women have completed secondary school and are working in food and beverage units in Navi Mumbai. More educated workers are also employed in this sector. A total of 57.14% of males from Navi Mumbai and 55.88% of females from the Central suburbs are graduates, but they are working in food and beverage units in the region. The educational achievement of the workers is increasing. Now more workers are graduates, and they join food and beverage units in region. Only 3.70% of males and 1.59% of females are postgraduates, but they are from the Western region. Postgraduate workers are very few in food and beverage units. The females who are postgraduate comprise only 1.59%. It might be that, at high skill and education levels, there is no work available, or the jobs are not well-paid. They might be working in other sectors with high paying jobs.

Table 5 - Personal Documents Of The GIG Workers In Mumbai (%)

Suburbs	Gender	Driving license	Drive 2 /4 Wheeler	Passport	Bank Account	Credit card	Debit card	Ration card
	M	26.85	18.52	13.88	77.78	4.63	20.37	6.48
Western	F	0.00	0.00	9.52	63.49	3.17	12.70	6.35
	T	16.95	11.70	12.28	72.51	4.09	17.54	6.43
	M	13.46	5.77	1.92	71.15	3.85	13.46	7.69
Central	F	0.00	0.00	5.88	52.94	2.94	17.65	0.00
	T	8.13	3.49	3.49	63.95	3.49	15.12	4.65
	M	7.69	7.69	0.00	76.92	0.00	15.38	0.00
Eastern	F	0.00	0.00	12.50	50.00	0.00	12.50	0.00
	T	4.76	4.76	4.76	66.67	0.00	14.29	0.00
	M	7.14	0.00	14.28	71.43	7.14	14.29	21.43
Navi Mumbai	F	0.00	0.00	0.00	62.50	0.00	12.50	0.00
	T	4.54	0.00	9.09	68.18	4.55	13.64	13.64
	M	20.32	12.83	9.62	75.40	4.28	17.65	7.49
Total	F	0.00	0.00	7.96	59.29	2.65	14.16	3.54
	T	12.66	8.00	9.00	69.33	3.67	16.33	6.00

Source: As per table 1

As far as driving licenses are concerned, 26.85% of males from the Western suburbs have it. Females do not have driving licenses in any suburb of region. The females may have lower income, or they may not be interested in learning to drive vehicles. Males (18.52%) drive 2/4 wheelers, but they are from the Western suburbs. Females do not drive 2/4 wheelers in any suburbs in the Mumbai region. A total of 13.88% of males from the Western suburbs and 12.50% of females from the Eastern suburbs have passports and are workers in food and beverage units. A passport can provide the opportunity to work in other countries. Workers can gain experience in this sector and apply for jobs in developed countries, which offer well-paid jobs. A total of 77.78% of males and 63.49% of females from the Western suburbs have bank accounts. Food and beverage units transfer the salaries of workers into bank accounts. Therefore, the majority of workers have savings accounts in commercial banks. Nearly 4.63 % of males and 3.17% of females from the Western suburbs have credit cards. Access to and use of credit cards is low among such workers. Their income is very low; therefore, they do not spend money through credit cards. A total of 20.37 % of males from the Western suburbs and 17.65 % of females from the Central suburbs have debit cards. Debit cards are useful for withdrawing money at any time from ATMs. Due to lower income, their use of debit cards is also limited. They tend to keep minimum cash in their pockets for various types of transactions. Around 21.43% of males from Navi Mumbai and 6.35% of females from the Western suburbs have ration cards. In urban areas, the government does not issue white ration cards, which provide free food such as wheat, sugar, and rice. Workers' incomes are above the poverty line, so they are not provided with such ration cards. Women are also more engaged in this sector. The rise of digital platforms has increased career opportunities and income potential, particularly for women (Sarker, M.R., Taj, T.A., Sarkar, M.A.R 2024). There are jobs available near their homes and in their areas. Women workers earn income from this sector with limited skills and education.

Table 6 - Monthly Income Of GIG Workers: (Rs. Thousands) (%)

Suburbs	Gender	10-20	20-30	30-40	40-50	50<
	M	25.93	35.19	24.07	10.19	4.63
Western	F	30.16	60.32	6.35	3.17	0.00
	T	27.49	44.44	17.54	7.60	2.92
Central	M	28.85	51.92	11.54	7.69	0.00
	F	35.29	58.82	5.88	0.00	0.00
	T	31.76	54.12	9.41	4.71	0.00
Eastern	M	23.08	30.77	30.77	15.38	0.00
	F	25.00	62.50	0.00	12.50	0.00
	T	23.81	42.86	19.05	14.29	0.00
Navi Mumbai	M	21.43	42.86	21.43	14.29	0.00
	F	37.50	62.50	0.00	0.00	0.00
	T	27.27	50.00	13.64	9.09	0.00
	M	26.20	40.11	20.86	10.16	2.67
Total	F	31.86	60.18	5.31	2.65	0.00
	T	28.33	47.67	15.00	7.33	1.67

Source: As per table 1

The monthly income for workers in this sector is very low. This is because not everyone goes to hotels every day. Females do not go to hotels regularly, but they do visit on different occasions along with their families. The food industry profits based on how many people eat at hotels in the region. Such habits and behaviour of people affect the income earned by workers in food and beverage units. Now a days, working men and women have habit to order food from Zomato and Swiggy apps. But order of online food depends on income earned by family. The income per month earned by gig workers in food and beverage industry is very low. The Males (28.85%) from the Central suburbs and females (37.50%) from Navi Mumbai are earning only Rs. 10,000-20,000 per month. This is a very low monthly salary, but workers are striving to sustain their lives in the city. Males (62.50%) from Navi Mumbai and females (62.50%) from the Eastern suburbs earn Rs. 20,000-30,000 per month. We don't know the nature of their jobs, but they are engaged in economic activities in this sector. Males (30.77%) from the Eastern suburbs and females (24.07%) from the Western suburbs have a monthly income of Rs. 30,000-40,000. 15.38% of males and 12.50% of females from the Eastern suburbs have incomes ranging from Rs. 40,000-50,000. They are likely working in either managerial or supervisory positions in this sector. Managers and supervisors have higher salaries along with additional administrative tasks. Males (4.63%) from the Western suburbs have incomes exceeding Rs. 50,000 from the food and beverage sector. Very few males have higher salaries in this sector. Males may have all the administrative responsibilities, which is why they would be paid more in this sector. We can also understand their standard of living through the different assets in their households.

Table 7 - Assets In House Of GIG Workers In Region (%)

Suburbs		Radio	Television	Oven	Bike	Cycle	Car	Washing Machine	Air Conditioner	Refrigerator
	M	9.29	75	14.81	55.55	28.7	1.85	10.18	51.85	77.77
Western	F	15.87	69.84	11.11	47.61	33.33	0	4.76	46.03	84.12
	T	11.7	73.1	13.45	52.63	30.41	1.17	8.19	49.71	80.12

Central	M	11.53	75	5.76	46.15	25	0	7.69	44.23	78.84
	F	14.7	70.58	14.7	50	29.41	0	8.82	55.88	79.41
	T	12.79	73.26	9.3	47.67	26.74	0	8.14	48.84	79.07
Eastern	M	7.69	53.84	15.38	69.23	15.38	0	7.69	46.15	76.92
	F	12.5	75	12.5	37.5	25	0	12.5	37.5	87.5
	T	9.52	61.9	14.29	57.14	19.05	0	9.52	42.86	80.95
Navi Mumbai	M	21.42	64.28	7.14	50	28.57	0	0	42.85	85.71
	F	0	75	12.5	62.5	12.5	0	12.5	37.5	87.5
	T	13.64	68.18	9.09	54.55	22.73	0	4.55	40.91	86.36
	M	10.69	72.72	11.76	53.47	26.73	1.06	8.55	48.66	78.6
Total	F	14.15	70.79	12.38	48.67	30.08	0	7.07	47.78	83.18
	T	12	72	12	51.67	28	0.67	8	48.33	80.33

Source: As per table 1

Total of 9.29% of males and 15.8% of females from the Western suburbs have radios at home. Very few workers listen to the radio nowadays. Around 75% of males and 70.58% of females from the Central suburbs have televisions at home. Every worker watch cinema, news, and serials on television. Around 15.38% of males and 12.5% of females have ovens at home, but they are from the Eastern suburbs. Overall, few workers of food and beverage sector have ovens at home. From the Eastern suburbs, 69.23% of males and 37.5% of females have bikes at home. Most males have bike, which is helpful for moving around their area or visiting nearby locations such as markets. A total of 28.7% of males and 33.3% of females have bicycles at home. From the Western suburbs, 1.85% of males have cars at home. Workers are very poor, so they cannot afford to own a car. Car also requires fuel, parking facilities, insurance, and maintenance. In Mumbai, the population density is very high. Workers travel by local trains to reach their workplaces. Local trains are getting crowded due to high growth of population and urbanisation in region. From the Eastern suburbs, 7.49% of males and 12.5% of females have washing machines at home. Very few workers have washing machines at home, so they wash their clothes on their own. At very low income, they cannot afford to buy costly physical assets at home. Buying a house for workers is also costlier in region. They prefer rental housing in region at longer distance in suburb. A total of 51.85% of males and 46.03% of females have air conditioning at home. Due to the humid climate of Mumbai, air conditioning is necessary. However, only half of the workers have air conditioning at home. A total of 85.71% of males and 87.5% of females from Navi Mumbai have refrigerator at home. Refrigerator is required to preserve perishable food. It certainly helps worker to preserve food and eat nutritious food. Through balanced diet, it helps to maintain good health status.

Table 8 - Social Security Benefits To Workers (%)

Social Security Benefits/Gender	Western			Central			Eastern			Navi Mumbai			Total		
	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T
Incentives for good work	39.81	39.68	39.77	34.61	47.05	39.53	53.84	25.00	42.86	42.85	37.50	40.91	39.57	40.70	40.00

Provident Fund	15.74	3.17	11.11	5.76	5.88	5.81	7.59	0.00	4.76	14.28	0.00	9.09	12.29	3.53	9.00
Regular salary hike	16.66	3.17	11.70	5.76	5.88	5.81	7.69	0.00	4.76	14.28	0.00	9.09	12.83	3.53	9.33
Dearness allowance	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.94	1.16	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.88	0.33
Sick leaves	91.66	98.41	94.15	100.00	97.05	98.84	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	95.18	98.23	96.33
Casual Leaves	92.59	93.65	92.98	100.00	97.05	98.84	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	95.72	95.57	95.67
Health Insurance	1.85	0.00	1.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.06	0.00	0.67
Maternity/ Paternity Leave	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Accident Insurance	0.92	0.00	0.58	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.53	0.00	0.33
Disability Benefit	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Overseas Trips	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Paid Leaves	14.81	4.76	9.76	5.76	8.82	7.29	15.38	0.00	7.69	14.28	0.00	7.14	12.29	5.30	8.79
Food assistance at job or Carry food everyday	89.81	96.82	90.86	96.15	94.11	95.68	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	93.04	96.46	94.67

Source: As per table 1

Nearly 53.84% of males and 25% of females from the Eastern suburbs received incentives for good work. Very few workers are provided with incentives for their work, which is not motivating them to work hard. Only 15.74% of males and 3.17% of females from the Western suburbs have provident fund contribution. Provident funds contribution is not provided to workers working in the food and beverage sector. A total of 16.66% of males and 3.17% of females from the Western suburbs reported that they had regular salary hikes. Workers are not paid regular increments in this sector; they leave one unit and join another unit if the salary is higher than previous unit. This reflects a rejection of contracts based on income and bargaining for it. All males and females from the Eastern suburbs and Navi Mumbai stated that they receive sick leave and casual leave. Sick and casual leave are provided to all workers in food and beverage units. We have not checked it with seasons of order and leaves given to workers by different units. During different seasons, workers of food and beverage units asked to work more hours and complete orders on time. Only 1.85% of males from the Western suburbs reported that they are receiving health insurance. Health insurance is not provided by food and beverage units, and workers need to buy insurance from private insurance companies, which provide insurance at very high premium. They do not afford to take health insurance policies. They depend on the

public health care facilities for medical treatment. Paternity and maternity leave are not received by any male and female worker in the region. All business units do not afford to give such benefits to its workers. Units must provide maternity leave to female workers. However, units often employ unmarried girls, and once they get married, the units terminate their work contract. It is the only short cut used by units to avoid the benefit of maternity leave to female workers. Males do not get any kind of paternity leave. Only 0.92% of males from the Western suburbs reported that they have accident insurance. Not a single worker has reported having overseas trips and disability benefits. These benefits are not provided to workers in this sector at Mumbai region. There is maximum risk for workers life during delivery of food through two wheelers. A total of 14.81% of males and 4.76% of females stated that they receive paid leaves. Almost all males and females carry their food from home in the Eastern suburbs, and they are from Navi Mumbai. Food is not provided to workers in hotels and restaurants. Workers are serving food, but they cannot eat food which is cooked in food and beverage unit. They have instruction from employer as not to eat such cooked food at units.

Job Satisfaction And Incentives:

Job satisfaction was analysed based on skill acquisition, work-life balance, contractual terms, and supervisor relationships. The workers have high satisfaction with skills acquired but limited plans for upskilling. The moderate satisfaction received by worker because of employer support and leave policies of the food and beverage unit. The low satisfaction is related to pay and incentives at job. The workers receive no maternity/paternity leave, provident fund, or dearness allowance in food and beverage industry. Job satisfaction is related to education and asset ownership. We have asked job satisfaction related questions to workers during primary survey.

Table 9 - Job Satisfaction Of Workers In Food And Beverage Sector (%)

Job satisfaction/Gender	Western			Central			Eastern			Navi Mumbai			Total		
	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T
Content with skills acquired for the job	72.2	73.01	72.51	80.76	85.29	82.56	76.92	75.00	76.19	92.85	50.00	77.27	76.47	75.22	76.00
Plan to upgrade skills	43.5	49.20	45.61	44.23	32.35	39.53	38.46	50.00	42.86	35.71	75.00	50.00	42.78	46.01	44.00
Happy with terms of contract	81.4	80.95	81.29	92.30	91.17	91.86	92.30	87.50	90.48	71.42	62.50	68.18	84.49	83.18	84.00
Work-life balance	49.0	55.55	51.46	55.76	41.17	50.00	61.53	50.00	57.14	64.28	50.00	59.09	52.94	50.44	52.00
Adequate support from employer	79.6	73.01	77.19	76.92	91.17	82.56	100.00	87.50	95.24	78.57	75.00	77.27	80.21	79.64	80.00
Relations with employer/management	20.3	26.98	22.81	23.07	8.82	17.44	0.00	12.50	4.76	21.42	25.00	22.73	19.78	20.35	20.00
Employer grant leave when needed	75.0	71.42	73.68	73.07	79.41	75.68	100.00	75.00	90.48	100.00	62.50	86.36	78.07	73.45	76.33
Recognition from supervisor for a job	17.5	80.95	19.88	13.46	94.11	11.63	7.69	10.00	14.29	21.42	75.00	22.73	16.04	85.84	17.33

well done								0							
Free to make decisions and act on them	24.07	20.63	22.81	26.92	32.35	29.07	15.38	25.00	19.05	21.42	12.50	18.18	24.06	23.89	24.00
Participation in supervisory duties that affect job	66.66	77.77	70.76	78.84	64.70	73.26	69.23	62.50	66.67	85.71	75.00	81.82	71.65	72.56	72.00
Closely observed by your supervisor	99.07	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	99.46	100.00	100.00
Satisfied with the department	14.81	20.63	16.96	19.23	17.64	18.60	0.00	0.00	0.00	21.42	0.00	13.64	15.50	16.81	16.00
Satisfaction with present salary	26.85	38.09	30.99	30.76	35.29	32.56	30.76	37.50	33.33	42.85	25.00	36.36	29.41	36.28	32.00

Source: As per table 1

A total of 80.76% of males and 85.29% of females said that they are content with the skills acquired on the job. Most of the workers learn how to take orders, deliver orders, and manage computer and app-based orders. This means they improve their working skills in this type of job. A total of 35.71% of males and 75% of females said that they plan to upgrade their skills. Workers are enthusiastic about improving their skills. From the Central suburbs, 92.30% of males and 91.17% of females were happy with the terms of their contracts. A total of 64.28% of males and 50% of females from Navi Mumbai said that they have a work-life balance, allowing them time for various family activities. All males and 87.50% of females from the Eastern suburbs said that they receive adequate support from their employers. A total of 20.37% of males and 26.98% of females from the Western suburbs said that they have good relations with their employer. Such good relations are important for receiving work assignments, appreciation, and salary hikes. From the Eastern suburbs, all men and 75% of females said that their employer grants leave when needed. In emergencies, leave is essential for workers. It is good that the units provide sick and casual leave promptly. Around 21.42% of males and 75% of females from Navi Mumbai said that they receive recognition from supervisors for a job well done. From the Central suburbs, 26.92% of males and 32.33% of females said that they are free to make decisions and act on them. The management of the units helps workers make decisions, which often aids in working efficiently. From Navi Mumbai, 85.71% of males and 75% of females said that their managers participate in supervisory duties that affect their jobs. However, managers sometimes unnecessarily disturb the duties and decisions made by workers. Only 19.23% of males and 17.64% of females from the Central suburbs said that they are satisfied with their department as it stands now. Only 42.85% of males and 25% of females from Navi Mumbai said that they are satisfied with their current salary. This indicates that workers in food and beverage units expect higher salaries, but higher salaries are not provided to them, while units continue to make profits from their business.

REGRESSION ANALYSIS

We are interested in finding the job satisfaction of workers in food and beverage units. This study defines job satisfaction as a work attitude that contributes to the physical and mental well-being of gig workers. It consists of five components: satisfaction with the work itself, satisfaction with superiors, satisfaction with colleagues, satisfaction with promotion opportunities, and satisfaction with remuneration (Chen Yang, 2023). We defined the logistic regression model to understand the socio-economic factors responsible for job satisfaction and performance of workers. A logistic regression model is defined as follows.

$$Z_i = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 \dots \dots \dots + \beta_K X_K + \varepsilon \quad (9)$$

Where Z_i is a linear sum of α and β_1 plus β_2 times X_2 and so on up to β_K times X_K . In above equation, α and β are intercept and slope. The z is an index that combines of X 's. Last, ϵ is error term.

$$Z = \frac{1}{1+e^{-Z}} \quad (10)$$

We can substitute Z in the right-hand side for Z to get Z equal 1 over 1 plus e minus the quantity α plus the sum of $\beta_1 X_1$ for i ranges from 1 to K . Therefore, the logistic model is written as

$$Z = \frac{1}{1+e^{-(\alpha+\beta_1 X_1)}} \quad (11)$$

Such model is used for job satisfaction of workers. Independent variables are socio-economic and demographic variables related to workers.

$$Z_i = (CSA + PUS + HTC + WLB + ASE + RE + EG + RSJ + COS + SPS) \quad (12)$$

Where, Z_i means job satisfaction of worker. The CSA is content with skills acquired for the job, PUS described as plan to upgrade skills, HTC stands for happy with terms of contract, WLB simply work-life balance. The ASE means adequate support from employer. The RE stands for relations with employer/management. We defined the EG as employer grant leave when needed, RSJ is recognition from supervisor for a job well done. The COS is observed by your supervisor. Lastly, SPS means satisfaction with present salary.

We categorised 1 as very high job satisfaction and 0 as no job satisfaction. We have used scale from 1 to 10. Job satisfaction is measured as very high satisfaction then we used 8–10 score. But if it is high satisfaction then 7–7.9 score is used. Suppose job satisfaction is acceptable satisfaction then 6–6.9 score used. The low satisfaction score is given as 5–5.9 and lastly very low satisfaction is given score as 0–4.9. If the dependent variable is scored as 8 to 10 then we defined it as very high satisfaction.

$$Z_i \geq 8 \quad (13)$$

We converted Y_{it} from 8 to 10 scale as very high job satisfaction to 1 otherwise 0. The nature of dependent variable is 1 as very high job satisfaction otherwise not which is defined as 0. We used logistic regression model because of nature of dependent variable in regression as either 1 or 0. We regressed dependent variable on independent variables such as socio-economic and demographic variables of workers working in food and beverage industry. The results are presented as follows.

Table 10 - Regression Analysis Of GIG Workers Of Food And Beverage Industry

Variables	Co-efficient	Standard Error	Wald Test
Secondary school	1.142**	.609	3.518
High secondary school	1.058**	.592	3.189
Graduate	.936**	.557	2.821
Incentive for good work	-1.069**	.331	10.439
Radio	-1.659*	.472	12.360
Bike	-1.817*	.371	24.031
Air condition	.757**	.320	5.588
Refrigerator	1.828*	.436	17.559
Constant	-2.034**	.627	10.535
-2 Log likelihood=312.787	Cox & Snell R Square=0.171	Nagelkerke R Square=0.237	R

Gig workers' job satisfaction in the food and beverage industry is positively correlated with secondary school, higher secondary school, and graduate education. This means higher education helps workers understand rules and regulations, technology, and secure higher pay at their jobs. Education certainly provides an advantage in smart work and work performance. The incentive for good work is negatively correlated with job satisfaction among workers in the food and beverage industry in the region. Workers are not paid more for their extra efforts. Customers want quality services, but workers are not compensated for putting in additional effort. All food deliveries are required to be on time, but incentives are not paid. That is why workers are in search of better employment opportunities with higher wages. Gig workers do not have radios at home, and they may not have time to listen to the radio either. Therefore, having a radio at home is negatively correlated with job satisfaction. Gig workers also do not own bikes, which is negatively correlated with job satisfaction. Having an air conditioner at home is positively correlated with job satisfaction among gig workers. Similarly, having a refrigerator at home is positively correlated with job satisfaction, and this relationship is statistically significant.

Policy Implications And Conclusion:

The gig economy continues to grow, but social security and fair compensation remain critical issues. Central government is planning to provide social security benefits to platform workers. But those workers working in small units and inside units, the social security benefits remain as unanswered question. There is need of implementing monetary and non-monetary incentives all workers working (e.g., performance-based pay, bonuses, and festival gifts) to gig workers in this sector. They must be ensuring regular salary hikes and annual increments by employer. They must be providing skill training and career growth opportunities. All workers must be provided paid leave every year. The young recently joined workforce, the female must have maternity leaves and male must be provided paternity benefits. The government must follow compulsory registration of units for social security schemes to workers beyond large platforms like Zomato and Swiggy. There is need to provide the support for mental and financial stress faced by gig workers. Effective policies can enhance the quality of work-life balance, improve job satisfaction, and ensure sustainable livelihoods for gig workers in the food and beverage sector in Mumbai.

Figure 1 Salary and number of workers

We can see from the diagram that the monthly salary is provided at the bottom of the diagram. With a 7% incentive, the efficiency of workers increases faster. If food and beverage units pay 12.5% incentives, then the salary of gig workers increases slightly. We can say that

salaries up to ten thousand can increase the incentives. For those who already receive lower salaries, the incentive policy will not work. This is because incentives tied to salary will increase only in small amounts. It will not provide any motivation for workers at lower salary levels to work hard. It is mainly including the supportive staff which is working at very low salary. Hence, workers must be provided with non-monetary incentives. They must be given regular hikes and annual increments in salary. Workers must also be paid overtime for good performance. Adequate technical training and skills should be provided for effective work. Paid leave must be granted every year, or in the event of any unfortunate incidents in workers' lives. Workers must be provided incentives in the form of gifts during Diwali, Christmas, and summer, such as kitchen related items, food items, groceries, clothes, electronic goods, etc. This will improve their standard of living and performance at work. Gig workers reported mental health and life satisfaction that are worse than those employed full-time and part-time (Wang S, Li LZ, Coutts A 2022). Workers must be provided with work that they enjoy. This will improve their well-being and reduce stress levels. The Central Government's Ministry of Labour and Employment has asked all gig workers to register themselves on the e-Shram portal. However, they made it mandatory for Zomato, Swiggy, and other big companies in the food and beverage sector. Workers in small units are not eligible to register on e-Shram for social security benefits. Therefore, an innovative social security model is required on urgent basis for the benefit of all workers in food and beverage units. All policies will certainly improve the welfare and standard of living of workers in this sector.

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